

FURYE ALMASHTIRISHIDAN FOYDALANIB INTEGRALLARNI HISOBLASH

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ANNOTATSIYA

Furye almashtirishlari yordamida matematik analizdagi ba'zi parametrga bog'liq xosmas integrallarni hisoblash muommosi yechiladi. Laplas integrallari va boshqa murakkab integrallar shular jumlasidandir.

***Kalit so'zlar:** furye almashtirishlari, Laplas integrallari, absolyut integrallanuvchi, juft funsiya, toq funksiya.*

Furye almashtirishlarining bugungi kunda hayotdagi tatbiqlari juda ko'p bo'lib, biz quyida integrallarni yechishdagi qulayligini qarab chiqamiz.

R sonlar o'qida absolyut integrallanuvchi f funksiya uchun

$$f^*(y) = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} f(x)e^{-iyx} dx \quad (1)$$

Integral almashtirish kiritamiz. Bunda f^* funksiya f ning Furye almashtirishi deyiladi.

$$f(x) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} f^*(y) e^{ixy} dy \quad (2)$$

Tenglikning o'ng tomonidagi birinchi tur xosmas integral yaqinlashsa, u holda f funksiya Furiye integraliga yoyiladi va (2) integral teskari Furiye almashtirishi deb ham ataladi.

$$e^{-ixy} = \cos xy - i \sin xy$$

Tenlikga ko'ra,

$$f^*(y) = A(y) - iB(y).$$

$$A(y) = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} f(x) \cos xy dx \quad B(y) = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} f(x) \sin xy dx$$

Yuqoridagilardan foydalanib (2) tenglik quyidagi kurinishni oladi.

$$\begin{aligned} f(x) &= \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} (A(y) - iB(y))(\cos xy + i \sin xy) dy \\ &= \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} [A(y) \cos xy + B(y) \sin xy] dy. \end{aligned}$$

a) Agar $f(x)$ funksiya juft funksiya bo'lsa, u holda

$$f(x) = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^{\infty} A(y) \cos xy dy$$

b) Agar $f(x)$ funksiya toq funksiya bo'lsa, u holda

$$f(x) = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^{\infty} B(y) \sin xy dy$$

Almashtirishlar o'rinli bo'ladi.

1-misol. Laplas inegralini hisoblang. $L_1 = \int_0^{\infty} \frac{\cos xy}{1+y^2} dy$.

Yechimi:

$$f(x) = \int_0^{\infty} \frac{\cos xy}{1+y^2} dy, \quad \text{yuqoridagi a) shartga ko'ra } f(x) \text{ funksiya juft funksiya}$$

ekanligi kelib chiqadi, a) shart bilan berilgan integralni tenglashtirsak;

$$\frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^{\infty} A(y) \cos xy \, dy = \int_0^{\infty} \frac{\cos xy}{1+y^2} \, dy$$

$$A(y) = \frac{\pi}{1+y^2}, \quad A(y) = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} f(x) \cos xy \, dx$$

Ekanligi ma'lum, $f(x)$ funksiyani juft funksiya ekanligini inobatga olsak,

$$\frac{\pi}{1+y^2} = 2 \int_0^{\infty} f(x) \cos xy \, dx$$

$$\int_0^{\infty} f(x) \cos xy \, dx = \frac{\pi}{2} \frac{1}{1+y^2}$$

$\int_0^{\infty} e^{-ax} \cos bx \, dx = \frac{a}{a^2+b^2}$ ekanligidan foydalanib, $f(x)$ funksiyani juft funksiya ekanligini hisobga olsak, yuqoridagi integral tenglikdan $f(x)$ funksiya quyidagiga tengligi kelib chiqadi;

$$f(x) = \frac{\pi}{2} e^{-|x|} \text{ yani}$$

$$\int_0^{\infty} \frac{\cos xy}{1+y^2} \, dy = \frac{\pi}{2} e^{-|x|}.$$

Tenglikka ega bo'lamiz.

2-misol. Laplas integralini hisoblang. $L_2 = \int_0^{\infty} \frac{y \sin xy}{1+y^2} \, dy$

Yechimi: $f(x) = \int_0^{\infty} \frac{y \sin xy}{1+y^2} \, dy$

Yuqoridagi b) shartga ko'ra $f(x)$ funksiya toq funksiya ekanligi kelib chiqadi. B) shart bilan yuqoridagi integrallarni tenglashtirsak,

$$\frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^{\infty} B(y) \sin xy \, dy = \int_0^{\infty} \frac{y \sin xy}{1+y^2} \, dy$$

$$B(y) = \frac{\pi y}{1+y^2}, \quad B(y) = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} f(x) \sin xy \, dx$$

Ekanligi ma'lum, $f(x)$ funksiyani toq funksiya ekanligini inobatga olsak;

$$\frac{\pi y}{1+y^2} = 2 \int_0^{\infty} f(x) \sin xy \, dx$$

$$\int_0^{\infty} f(x) \sin xy \, dx = \frac{\pi}{2} \frac{y}{1+y^2}$$

$\int_0^{\infty} e^{-ax} \sin bx \, dx = \frac{b}{a^2+b^2}$ tenlikdan va $f(x)$ funksiyani toq funksiya ekanligigan foydalanib yuqoridagi integral tenlikni yechsak, $f(x)$ funksiya quyidagiga teng bo'ladi;

$$f(x) = \frac{\pi}{2} \operatorname{sgn} x e^{-|x|}$$

Demak, $\int_0^{\infty} \frac{y \sin xy}{1+y^2} dy = \frac{\pi}{2} \operatorname{sgn} x e^{-|x|}$ tenglikka ega b'lamiz.

3-misol. Integralni hisoblang.

$$\int_0^{\infty} \left[\frac{1}{(y-b)^2+a^2} + \frac{1}{(y+b)^2+a^2} \right] \cos xy \, dy$$

Yechimi: $f(x) = \int_0^{\infty} \left[\frac{1}{(y-b)^2+a^2} + \frac{1}{(y+b)^2+a^2} \right] \cos xy \, dy$

Yuqoridagi a) shartga ko'ra $f(x)$ funksiyaning juft funksiya ekanligi kelib chiqadi.

A) shartni va yuqoridagi integralni tenglashtirsak,

$$\frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^{\infty} A(y) \cos xy \, dy = \int_0^{\infty} \left[\frac{1}{(y-b)^2+a^2} + \frac{1}{(y+b)^2+a^2} \right] \cos xy \, dy$$

$$\begin{aligned} A(y) &= \pi \left[\frac{1}{(y-b)^2+a^2} + \frac{1}{(y+b)^2+a^2} \right], \quad A(y) \\ &= \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} f(x) \cos xy \, dx \end{aligned}$$

Ekanligi ma'lum, $f(x)$ funksiyani juft funksiya ekanligini inobatga olsak,

$$\int_0^{\infty} f(x) \cos xy \, dx = \frac{\pi}{2} \left[\frac{1}{(y-b)^2+a^2} + \frac{1}{(y+b)^2+a^2} \right]$$

Ushbu tenglikdan $f(x)$ funksiyani topish uchun quyidagi formulalardan foydalanamiz,

$$\cos yx * \cos bx = \frac{1}{2} [\cos(y - b)x + \cos(y + b)x]$$

$$I_1 = \int_0^{\infty} e^{-ax} \cos(y - b)x dx = \frac{a}{(y - b)^2 + a^2}$$

$$I_2 = \int_0^{\infty} e^{-ax} \cos(y + b)x dx = \frac{a}{(y + b)^2 + a^2}$$

Biz topishimiz kerak bo'lgan $f(x)$ funksiyaning juftligini va yuqoridagi formulalarni hisobga olsak, $f(x)$ funksiya quyidagiga teng ekanligi kelib chiqadi;

$$f(x) = \frac{\pi}{a} e^{-a|x|} \cos bx$$

Demak, $\int_0^{\infty} \left[\frac{1}{(y-b)^2+a^2} + \frac{1}{(y+b)^2+a^2} \right] \cos xy dy = \frac{\pi}{a} e^{-a|x|} \cos bx$ tenglikka ega bo'lamiz.

4-misol. Integralni hisoblang.

$$\int_0^{\infty} \frac{y \sin xy}{[(y - b)^2 + a^2][(y + b)^2 + a^2]} dy$$

Yechimi: $f(x) = \int_0^{\infty} \frac{y \sin xy}{[(y-b)^2+a^2][(y+b)^2+a^2]} dy$

Yuqoridagi b) shartga ko'ra $f(x)$ funksiyaning toq funksiya ekanligi kelib chiqadi.

B) shartni va berilgan integrallarni tenglashtirsak,

$$\frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^{\infty} B(y) \sin xy dy = \int_0^{\infty} \frac{y \sin xy}{[(y - b)^2 + a^2][(y + b)^2 + a^2]} dy$$

$$B(y) = \frac{\pi y}{[(y - b)^2 + a^2][(y + b)^2 + a^2]}, \quad B(y) = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} f(x) \sin xy dx$$

Ekanligi ma'lum, $f(x)$ funksiyaning toq funksiya ekanligini inobatga olsak,

$$\int_0^{\infty} f(x) \sin xy dx = \frac{\pi}{2} \frac{y}{[(y - b)^2 + a^2][(y + b)^2 + a^2]}$$

$$\int_0^{\infty} f(x) \sin xy \, dx = \frac{\pi}{8b} \left[\frac{1}{(y-b)^2 + a^2} - \frac{1}{(y+b)^2 + a^2} \right]$$

Ushbu tenglikdan $f(x)$ funksiyani topish uchun quyidagi formulalardan foydalanamiz,

$$\sin yx * \sin bx = \frac{1}{2} [\cos(y-b)x - \cos(y+b)x]$$

Va yuqoridagi I_1, I_2 integrallarni, $f(x)$ funksiyaning toq funksiya ekanligini hisobga olgan holda $f(x)$ funksiyani topsak, u quyidagiga teng bo'ladi.

$$f(x) = \frac{\pi}{4ab} e^{-a|x|} \sin bx$$

Demak,

$$\int_0^{\infty} \frac{y \sin xy}{[(y-b)^2 + a^2][(y+b)^2 + a^2]} \, dy = \frac{\pi}{4ab} e^{-a|x|} \sin bx$$

Tenglikka ega bo'lamiz

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